

Hair Analysis: An Innovative Biomonitoring Tool to Assess Human Exposure to Tri-Cresyl-Phosphate (TCP)

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ABBREVIATIONS

TCP Tri-Cresyl-Phosphate

ABSTRACT

Organophosphate flame retardants, especially Tri-Cresyl-Phosphate (TCP), are found in aircraft cabin air. They are strongly suspected to be related with aerotoxic syndrome that affects aircraft crews. Exposure information is stored in hair structure during hair synthesis and therefore hair matrix is a powerful biomonitoring tool to assess human exposure to xenobiotics over several months.

Analytical protocol was developed and validated to accurately measure level of 5 TCP isomers in hair matrix. The method was applied to investigate TCP exposure of crew members (N=46) and non-crew control group (N=35). A threshold value is proposed to attest for over-exposure to TCP.

INTRODUCTION

A recent study performed by EASA to assess cabin air quality demonstrated contamination by many organic compounds.¹ Among cabin air pollutants, organophosphate flame retardants were measured at significant levels in the air. Due to their well-known neurotoxicity, they are strongly suspected to be related to aerotoxic syndrome that affects aircraft crews. Beside Tri-Butyl-Phosphate (TBP, CAS 126-73-8), Tri-Phenyl-Phosphate (TPP, CAS 115-86-6) and Tri-Chloro-iso-Propyl-Phosphate (TCPP, CAS 13674-84-5) that are widely used in furniture and plastic, specific forms of

Figure 1—Chemical formula for Tri-ooo-Cresyl-Phosphate isomer

Tri-Cresyl-Phosphate (TCP) are used in Mobil Jet Oil II, the most widely used aircraft oil. Symptoms of aerotoxic syndrome are reported to occur after a fume event when air cabin is contaminated with oil residues and acutely expose aircraft crew and passengers to highly toxic substances that are in the oils. Initially, Mobil Jet Oil II contained higher levels of the TCP ortho isomers (Figure 1) than currently present in the TCP formulation used today. The reduction in the ortho isomer content was in part due to concerns being raised about its toxicity in relation to Organophosphate-induced delayed neuropathy (OPIDN). TCP composition of Mobil Jet Oil II was accurately determined in the work of Megson in 2016 and established the presence of 4 TCP isomers (3 - 5%): TmmmCP, TmmpCP, TmppCP, TpppCP with a specific ratio pattern.² The same kind of pattern was found in EASA Air Cabin contamination Study.

Blood and urine are considered as reference matrices for the biomonitoring of exposure to xenobiotics. However, their detection windows are very limited and biological samples need to be taken quickly after exposure: few hours for blood and a day for urine. Moreover, sampling blood requires medical assistance (venepuncture), blood and urine need to be frozen (-18°C or -60°C) and keep frozen during transport to the laboratory. As they are still “active” biological matrices, analysis should be done as soon as possible to avoid any degradation of the xenobiotic with high biohazard risk (Virus, HIV, hepatitis) for laboratory personnel. These limitations make blood and urine not suitable matrices for easy and user-friendly

Figure 2 — Detection window of hair and exposure period

biomonitoring tool.

As an alternative biological matrix, hair has been widely used for several decades to assess human exposure to alcohol, drug of abuse and environmental contaminants (persistent organic pollutant, pesticides...)³⁻⁵ Hair growth rate is about 1 cm per month. Hair root is irrigated with blood vessels. During hair synthesis in the scalp, xenobiotic present in blood stream incorporate the internal structure of hair. Compared to blood and urine, hairs are easier to sample, to ship (less than 20g with envelop and sampling form, ambient temperature) and to store (+5°C / -18°C, limited space needed). Moreover, exposure information stored in hair is very stable over time and analysis of 1 cm hair length is used to assess the average exposure over 1-month period (Figure 2). Even if the relationship between concentration found in hair and the average exposed dose cannot be obtained for humans, quantity measured in hair reflect the intensity of exposure and people with highest concentration are assumed to be more exposed. Study performed on rats demonstrated such relationship and can be reasonably assumed for human.⁶

IRES laboratory developed sampling procedure, collection kit and analysis protocol for the determination of TCP in hair to attest for exposure. Briefly, hair strand is cut to keep the first 3 cm of proximal (closest to the scalp) or specific segment length. Selected hair segment are washed to remove potential external contamination (environmental surface contamination) and grinded to get a fine powder. Accurate mass of hair's powder is extracted with organic solvents and the extract is analysed with gas

chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry detector (GC-MSMS). In terms of performance, five isomers of TCP (ToooCP, TmmmCP, TmmpCP, TmppCP and TpppCP) are measured in hair; the method has a limit of quantification (LoQ) of 2 pg/mg of hair and uncertainty ranging from 25% at LoQ and 20% at higher level.

A measurement campaign was performed to validate the protocol with real samples and obtain statistical information about TCP residues for crew members (N=46) and non-crew control group (N = 35). Results (Figure 3) attested exposure to at least one TCP isomer for more than 1 person out of 2 (53.2% for TmmpCP isomer) and TCP isomers found in Mobil Jet Oil II have the highest occurrences. Lowest occurrence was found for ToooCP (15.5%).

Due to small number of subjects (N = 81), only limited statistical interpretation were made. For data analysis, subjects with highest exposure level (highest concentration) were excluded using Grubb's test. Less than 5% samples (N = 4, 3 from Crew group and 1 from non-crew group) were excluded.

There are no significant difference between the two groups regarding occurrence and exposure level. Results obtained for non-crew group population strongly suggest environmental exposure to TCP and need to be investigated further in particular to determine the origin of exposure as TCP is not a flame retardant commonly used in domestic goods.

The TCP isomers pattern observed Mobil Jet Oil II is very close to the pattern found for occurrence ratio and average hair concentration (N = 77). This observation demonstrates with high probability human exposure to Mobil Jet Oil II.

Based on average concentration level and standard deviation, a threshold value was calculated with 95% confidence to attest for over-exposure to TCP. Hair taken from wife or husband (non-crew) of over exposed crew (N = 2) were tested for TCP over the same time period and no TCP was found. Difference observed strongly suggests occupational exposure to Mobil Jet II oil residues.

A sampling procedure and sensitive, accurate and reliable analytical protocol were successfully developed and validated for field investigation and promise to be a powerful biomonitoring tool for large scale campaign to search for correlation between TCP exposure and aerotoxic syndrome pathologies. Complete home testing kits are now available worldwide to assess human exposure to TCP.

Acknowledgment

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